

Supplementary material – data extraction form

Post-discharge Care Interventions to Support Patient Recovery after Elective Degenerative Spine Surgery – a systematic review

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This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)	26-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data	MDL	
Author(s)	Chen et al.	
Country	Taiwan	
Publication year	2015	
Title of article	Is rehabilitation intervention during hospitalization enough for functional improvements in patients undergoing lumbar decompression surgery? A prospective randomized controlled study	
Title of journal	Clinical Neurology and Neurosurgery	
Volume 129	Issue S1	Pages s41-s46
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)	Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & %/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial The patients were randomly allocated to either the perioperative group (PG) or the control group (CG) by a health professional	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	S41 title p. S42
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants	Patients scheduled for decompression surgery for lumbar stenosis	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. S42

Types of intervention	Rehabilitation intervention during hospitalization	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Types of comparison	Usual care: The control group (CG) received only instructions concerning post-operative care from the involved neurosurgical team.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Types of outcome measures	Pain Function disability/status Quality of life Activity Overall improvement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	The outcomes of patients after lumbar decompression surgery receiving perioperative rehabilitation	p. S42
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	A prospective randomised controlled trial	Title
Start date	December 2012	p. S43
End date	May 2012 (reported wrong? Must have been May 2013)	p. S43
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear Not reported. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Review Board/ Chang Gung Memorial Hospital (IRB/ CGMH).	p. S42

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Not reported	
Inclusion criteria	Inclusion criteria were: (1) between 18-65 years of age, (2) receiving primary LDS, and (3) able to communicate and actively participate in the program.	p. S42

Exclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria were: (1) mental disability, (2) severe neurological disease as well as contraindication to surgery in general, or (3) musculoskeletal or systemic disorders with functional impairments that limit tolerance to testing.	p. S42
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear All patients who met the inclusion criteria were given oral information and written consent of the study on admission.	p. S42

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Perioperative group (PG)	p. S42
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=29 (M:16, F:13) Mean age: 51.8	p. S44 Table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	On admission, the physiotherapist informed the patient about the protocol of the rehabilitation intervention during hospital stay in addition to the usual care and its continuance as a home program following discharge from hospital. As for early postoperative mobilization strategies, the patients were advised to stay active while wearing the lumbar corset and to sit less than 30 minutes at a time for one month after surgery, and they practiced mobility skills including how to move safely in bed or leave bed. Moreover, the physiotherapist mobilized the patients to get out of beds as early as possible and practice the rehabilitative protocol for 30 minutes daily during hospitalization. The rehabilitative protocol included not only deep breathing exercises but also trunk and extremity exercises since maintaining spinal posture and stabilization during activities of daily life was emphasized. The entire protocol was delivered by a researcher (CWC) 30 minutes a day during hospitalization for the PG only.	

Control group

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Control group (CG)	p. S42
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=31 (M:14, F:17) Mean age: 52.1	p. S44 Table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	The CG received only instructions concerning post-operative care by the involved neurosurgical team, i.e., the usual care protocol.	p. S42

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain (Back pain, LE pain)	Table 3, p. S45
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Visual Analog Scale (VAS) Back pain favors intervention, leg pain favors control	Table 3, p. S45 Table 3

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Function disability /status	Table 3, p. S45
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Roland-Morris disability questionnaire (RMDQ) Favors control	Table 3, p. S45

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Quality of life	Table 3, p. S45

Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	12-item Short Form Survey (SF-12) No difference	Table 3, p. S45
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Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	Activity	Table 3, p. S45
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	1) 5 repeated sit to stands, 2) timed 15 m. walk, 3) 1-minute going up and down stairs 1+3) No difference, 2) 15 m. walking favors control	Table 3, p. S45

Follow-up

Follow-up	6 months – 50 % lost to follow-up	p. S44 figure 1
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Conclusion	This study examined a rehabilitation program during hospitalization for patients who underwent LDS, and demonstrates the resulting improvements in pain, disability, and quality of life (in terms of mental health). Providing a rehabilitation program during hospitalization only had limited effects on functional performance up to the 6-month follow-up in patients who received LDS. The study suggests that task-oriented rehabilitative programs should be designed for functional performance, such as walking and stairs climbing. The programs should consider functional requirements for daily activities and provide regular support for patient adherence to execute the intervention program.	p. S45

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>